

Studies on Hydrodynamic Permeability of Aqueous Solutions of Glucose, Urea and Glucose-Urea Mixtures across Titanium Oxide Membrane

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Hydrodynamic permeabilities of aqueous solutions of glucose, urea and glucose-urea mixtures have been measured across a titanium oxide membrane. The hydrodynamic permeability decreases with increase in concentration of glucose, urea and glucose-urea mixtures at constant urea concentration. Both sides of the membrane have shown equal flows, the membrane is therefore isotropic. Results have been analysed in terms of the methodology of non-equilibrium thermodynamics.

Transport phenomena across membranes are quite complex owing to the complex surface characteristics. However, experimental studies in which the nature of the barrier and the nature of the permeating species are varied can give useful information. The effect of hydrostatic pressure across biological systems¹ has revealed interesting results. In the present study, attempts have been made to study the effect of concentration on the hydrodynamic permeabilities across titanium oxide membrane using glucose and urea mixtures. Urea (the major constituent of urine), glucose (the presence of which in urine causes renal glucosuria), and a mixture of these are of special significance² since any of these may at one time be an excretion product and at other time an indispensable metabolite. Since the mere presence of very small amount of glucose in urine increases micturition rate, therefore the permeation study of glucose-urea mixtures qualifies additional importance.

Results and Discussion

The permeability of a membrane depends upon the molecular size of the permeant, the pores of the membrane, the density and viscosity of the permeant, the state of aggregation of the liquid state, the solubility of the permeant in the membrane, the number of hydrogen bonds etc. None of the properties described above alone determines the behaviour of the membrane. Before putting a membrane into practical use, it is essential to know its characteristics, viz. effective cross-sectional area, equivalent pore radius and the electrical character of the membrane, which has been determined in the present membrane of titanium oxide as follows:

Membrane characterisation: The rate of permeation through a membrane under the influence of hydrostatic pressure depends upon the effective cross-sectional area (A) and the thickness

(l) of the membrane³. An unambiguous determination of either of these quantities is difficult due to the complex geometry of the pores within the membrane. It is, however, possible to determine the ratio A/l , the so called membrane constant, in terms of which the permeant behaviour of any membrane can be expressed quantitatively.

For a membrane having n pores of equivalent radius r , the effective cross-sectional area (A), through which permeation occurs is $n\pi r^2$. The electrical conductance (K) of the membrane equilibrated with a permeant having specific conductance (k) is given by⁴,

$$K = n\pi r^2 \cdot k/l = (A/l) \cdot k \quad (1)$$

so that the membrane constant is

$$\frac{K}{k} = \frac{A}{l} \quad (2)$$

This constant is a characteristic parameter of the membrane and is independent of the nature of the permeating liquid, as long as the interaction between the permeant and the membrane matrix is not strong enough to alter its equivalent pore radius⁴. The average pore radius can be evaluated from the relation,

$$\left(\frac{J_v}{\Delta P} \right) \Delta \pi = 0 = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l} = \frac{n\pi r^2 \times r^2}{1 \times 8\eta} = \frac{A}{l} \cdot \frac{r^2}{8\eta}$$

or

$$r = \left[\frac{8\eta (J_v / \Delta P) \Delta \pi = 0}{A/l} \right]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where η is the viscosity of the permeant, J_v the volume flow, ΔP the pressure difference (cm) of the permeant and $\Delta \pi$ the osmotic pressure difference.

The values of the equivalent pore radius and other characteristics ascertained from hydrodynamic permeability data for different aqueous solutions of glucose, urea and glucose-urea mixtures at 308 K are given in Table 1. It is evident from the result that the value of the membrane constant (A/l) is fairly constant for different solutions of glucose, urea and glucose-urea mixtures and is thus in accordance with the findings of Singh *et al.*⁴. In other words, the membrane constant is a characteristics of membrane only and is independent of the nature of the permeating liquid.

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE CHARACTERISTICS ASCERTAINED FROM HYDRODYNAMIC PERMEABILITY DATA FOR DIFFERENT AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF GLUCOSE, UREA AND GLUCOSE IN 1*m* UREA AT 308 K

Concn. mol/kg	$10^5 K \Omega^{-1}$	$10^5 k \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	A/l cm	$10^5 r$ cm
Glucose				
0.002	1.80	6.70	0.268	1.92
0.004	2.00	7.10	0.282	1.63
0.006	2.30	8.20	0.280	1.60
0.008	2.40	8.60	0.279	1.56
0.010	2.60	9.30	0.280	1.53
0.012	2.90	10.20	0.284	1.46
Urea				
0.20	2.30	8.35	0.276	1.75
0.40	4.40	15.52	0.284	1.70
0.60	5.20	18.36	0.283	1.65
0.80	6.20	21.99	0.282	1.63
1.00	7.30	25.73	0.284	1.59
Glucose in 1 <i>m</i> urea				
0.002	6.90	24.64	0.280	1.60
0.004	5.84	20.86	0.280	1.57
0.006	5.48	19.43	0.282	1.53
0.008	5.22	18.56	0.283	1.52
0.010	4.94	17.75	0.278	1.49
0.012	4.72	16.88	0.280	1.44

It is also evident from Table 1 that the equivalent pore radius decreases continuously with the increase in concentration of glucose, urea and glucose in 1*m* urea at 308 K. The equivalent pore radius is different for different permeating aqueous solutions, indicating thereby that the equivalent pore radius is not the characteristic property of the membrane only but it is seriously influenced by the nature of the permeating fluid.

Filtration coefficient (L_p): L_p is a permeability coefficient related to pressure difference and is a measure of the complexity of the membrane. In order to verify if any difference of concentration exists across the membrane, measurements of density, viscosity and refractive index were made before and after the experiment. It was found that no significant change occurred in these properties. Thus, a concentration difference across the membrane is ruled out.

The thermodynamic relation for the volume flow (J_v) as a function of applied pressure difference (ΔP) and osmotic difference ($\Delta\pi$) across the membrane is given by

$$J_v = L_p \Delta P - \sigma L_p \Delta \pi \quad (4)$$

where the symbols have their usual significance. It is convenient to determine the filtration coefficient L_p at $\Delta\pi=0$ or at equal concentrations of the solute on both sides of the membrane. Hence we get,

$$L_p = \left(-\frac{J_v}{\Delta P} \right)_{\Delta\pi=0} \quad (5)$$

The experiments show that the volume transported per unit time is linearly proportional to the pressure head. A sample plot for glucose at 308 K is shown in Fig. 1. The filtration coefficient L_p is obtained from the slopes of these linear plots. The values of L_p for aqueous solutions of glucose, urea, and glucose in 1*m* urea at 308 K are given in Table 2. The results show that the filtration coefficient decreases with the increase in concentration of glucose, urea and glucose in 1*m* urea. The variation of L_p with concentration of glucose in water and in 1*m* urea is shown in Fig. 2. The values of L_p are different for various aqueous solutions showing

Fig. 1. Plots of J_v vs ΔP for various concentration of glucose in water at 308 K: (Δ) 0.002, (O) 0.004, (\square) 0.006, (\blacktriangle) 0.008, (\bullet) 0.010 and (\blacksquare) 0.012 *m* glucose.

thereby that L_p is a characteristic of the membrane as well as that of the permeating liquid.

Since $\Delta\pi = RT\Delta C$, the relation (6) can also be written as

$$J'_v = L'_p (\Delta P' - RT\Delta C) \quad (7)$$

where J'_v is the resultant or net volume flow, R the gas constant, T the absolute temperature and ΔC the concentration difference across the membrane. According to equation (7), the plots of J'_v versus $\Delta P'$ should be a straight line and it has been found to be so as shown in Fig. 3 (a sample plot for various concentrations of glucose in water). The coefficient L'_p is estimated from the straight line and $(J'_v)_{\Delta P'=0}$ by the intercept respectively. It is evident from Fig. 3 that $(J'_v)_{\Delta P'=0}$ and L'_p are different for different concentrations of a particular solute. The values of L'_p thus estimated are given in Table 3.

TABLE 2—MECHANICAL FILTRATION COEFFICIENT (L_p) FOR VARIOUS AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF GLUCOSE, UREA AND GLUCOSE IN 1M UREA AT 308 K

Concn. mol/kg		$10^9 L_p$ $\text{cm}^3 \text{ dyn}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
	Glucose	
0.002		1.70
0.004		1.30
0.006		1.24
0.008		1.17
0.010		1.12
0.012		1.03
	Urea	
0.20		1.44
0.40		1.39
0.60		1.29
0.80		1.24
1.00		1.19
	Glucose in 1m urea	
0.002		1.18
0.004		1.14
0.006		1.09
0.008		1.07
0.010		1.02
0.012		0.96

Fig. 2. Filtration coefficient (L_p) as a function of solute concentration at 308 K: (O) glucose in water and (Δ) glucose in 1m urea.

Rejection or coupling coefficient (σ): The coupling coefficient (σ) was estimated from the relation,

$$J'_v = L'_p (\Delta P' - \sigma \Delta \pi) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3. Plots of J'_v vs $\Delta P'$ for various concentration of glucose in water at 308 K: (Δ) 0.002, (O) 0.004, (\square) 0.006, (Δ) 0.008, (\bullet) 0.010 and (\blacksquare) 0.012 m glucose.

TABLE 3—PERMEABILITY DATA AND REFLECTION COEFFICIENT (σ) FOR VARIOUS CONCENTRATION DIFFERENCES (ΔC) ACROSS THE MEMBRANE AT 308 K

ΔC mol/kg	$10^9 L_p$ $\text{cm}^5 \text{dyn}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	$10^5 \sigma$
Glucose		
0.002	1.70	7.63
0.004	1.55	6.21
0.006	1.43	1.66
0.008	1.30	1.06
0.010	1.25	0.62
0.012	1.13	0.29
Urea		
0.20	1.73	0.072
0.40	1.64	0.031
0.60	1.50	0.017
0.80	1.38	0.008
1.00	1.32	0.005
Glucose in 1 <i>m</i> urea		
0.002	1.35	10.04
0.004	1.32	4.73
0.006	1.28	2.83
0.008	1.19	2.06
0.010	1.10	1.57
0.012	1.03	1.05

If the hydrostatic pressure across the membrane is kept constant, i.e. $\Delta P' = 0$, then equation (7) can be written as

$$(J'_v)_{\Delta P'=0} = -\sigma L'_p RT \Delta C$$

or

$$\sigma = - \left[\frac{J'_v}{L'_p RT \Delta C} \right]_{\Delta P'=0} \quad (8)$$

The negative sign indicates that the hydrostatic and osmotic forces act in opposite directions. The values of σ so determined from relation (8) for different aqueous solutions of glucose, urea and glucose in 1*m* urea are also recorded in Table 3.

The rejection coefficient (σ) is the measure of the membrane selectivity and according to Staverman⁶, when $\sigma = 1$, all the solute is rejected by the membrane, while $\sigma < 1$ means a part of the solute passes through the membrane. In terms of velocities of the solute and solvent, σ can be interpreted as follows. When $\sigma = 1$, the velocity of solute is zero, meaning thereby that the solute cannot cross the membrane, and when $\sigma = 0$, the the solute and solvent move at equal rates through the membrane. According to pore model⁷ for the transport of non-electrolytes through membranes, the rejection coefficient is known as coupling coefficient measuring the coupling between the total volume flux and the solute transmission. As the value of σ tends towards zero, the coupling increases and when σ becomes equal to zero the coupling is complete which is possible only when the solute is identical with the solvent. It is clear from Table 3 that the value of σ decreases with increase in solute concentration. Besides, σ 's approach to zero, indicates that the coupling increases and the solute and solvent flow with nearly equal velocities at higher concentrations of the solute.

Activation parameters: The hydrodynamic permeability of fluids through porous media varies exponentially with temperature⁸, and is characterised in terms of activation energy⁹. In order to obtain activation energy and hence the free energy of activation, the hydrodynamic permeabilities for 1*m* urea in water and glucose in 1*m* aqueous urea were determined at different temperatures. The compatibility of equation,

$$(J_v)_{\Delta \pi=0} = L_p \Delta P \quad (9)$$

with Poissuille's law requires that

$$L_p = \pi \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} r_i^4 / 8 \eta l \quad (10)$$

where r is the radius of the i -th capillary, n the number of capillaries or pores in the membrane, η the viscosity of the permeant and l the thickness of the membrane. The variation of η of a liquid with temperature can be expressed as an activation process,

$$\eta = A e^{E_n/RT} \quad (11)$$

where A is a constant and E_n the activation energy. Substituting equation (11) into (10) and taking the logarithms,

$$\log L_p = K - E_n/RT \quad (12)$$

$$\text{where } K = \log \pi \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} r_i^4 / 8Al = \text{constant} \quad (13)$$

According to relation (12) a plot of $\log L_p$ versus $1/T$ should be linear and the same has found to be true. The slope of the linear plot gives the value of activation energy (E_n) which can be taken as enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) for viscous flow across the membrane and these values for 1*m* urea and glucose in 1*m* urea are given in Table 4.

The entropy of activation can be estimated from the Eyring rate equation⁸

$$\eta = \frac{Nh}{V} \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta S^*}{R} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\Delta H^*}{RT} \right) \quad (14)$$

 TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF GLUCOSE IN 1*m* UREA

Glucose mol/kg	ΔH^* kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS_{303}^* $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	ΔG_{303}^* kJ mol^{-1}
0.000	5.27	-0.03	5.28
0.002	6.65	4.52	5.28
0.004	6.64	4.47	5.29
0.006	6.28	3.25	5.29
0.008	5.94	2.11	5.30
0.010	5.70	1.32	5.30
0.012	5.06	-0.83	5.31

where η is the viscosity of permeant, N the Avogadro number, h the Planck constant, V the

molar volume of the permeant and ΔS^* the entropy of activation. Equation (14) can also be rearranged as

$$\Delta S^* = \frac{\Delta H^*}{T} + R \log (Nh/V\eta) \quad (15)$$

The values of ΔS^* derived from equation (15) at 303 K are also recorded in Table 4. It is clear that the value of ΔS^* is negative for 1*m* aqueous urea and becomes positive on the addition of glucose and further decreases with the increase in concentration of glucose and again becomes negative at 0.012*m* glucose. The negative sign associated with ΔS^* for 1*m* aqueous urea may be attributed to a state of high order. On the addition of small amounts of glucose to 1*m* urea the high order is disturbed and more disorder is introduced.

The values of the free energy of activation (ΔG^*) were calculated at 303 K from the relation,

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^* \quad (16)$$

and are also recorded in Table 4. A perusal of results shows that the values of ΔG^* are positive for 1*m* aqueous urea and glucose in 1*m* urea, meaning thereby that the flow across the membrane is not facilitated/favoured by these solutes in water. In other words, it may be said that until an input force is applied across the membrane, the flow of the permeant can not take place.

Experimental

The fluids selected for permeation were aqueous solutions of glucose, urea and mixtures of glucose-urea. Glucose and urea (AnalaR) were used without further purification. Double-distilled water was used.

The titanium oxide (SD Fine Chemicals) was swollen in conductivity water and casted in the form of a plug as described below. The swollen material (8.489 g) along with small amount (4–5%) of an adhesive (araldite) was placed in a pyrex glass tube having a constriction in the middle and compressed mechanically at the site of constriction. It was left as such for about 24 h for the complete setting of the plug (1.82 cm dia \times 1.25 cm). The maximum variation in the permeability of titanium oxide membrane thus prepared for a period of one week, was only of the order of 5%.

In order to know the directional character of the membrane for the permeation of water, the flow/hydraulic permeability was measured in both the directions at 303 K and the values were found to be the same in both the directions thereby indicating the isotropic character of the membrane.

The design of the apparatus and its experimental set up is the same as described in a previous communication¹⁰.

Procedure: The apparatus was filled with water and left overnight for equilibration of the plug. It was then thoroughly washed with distilled water under pressure gradient to ensure the thorough cleanliness. The apparatus was filled by adding the conductivity water on one side of the membrane and then sucking it to the other side under a pressure gradient by means of a vacuum pump. This ensured the complete filling of the capillaries of the membrane. It was then suitably mounted inside a thermostat to attain a constant temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). Then a constant hydraulic pressure head ΔP was imposed by maintaining a constant difference in levels of the liquid across the membrane. The hydrodynamic permeability was measured by following the displacement of the liquid meniscas in a horizontal graduated capillary tube of known diameter with the help of cathetometer sensitive to 0.001 cm. The time was noted. The experiment was repeated at other hydraulic pressure heads across the membrane. Further, the flow for different solutions was also measured similarly by replacing water with appropriate solutions on both sides of the membrane.

Conductance of the cell (membrane plus solution) and the specific conductivity of the permeant were measured with the help of a conductivity bridge (model 732) supplied by Naina Electronics Corporation (India). Viscosity was determined by the suspended capillary viscometer. For the evaluation of the rejection or coupling coefficient (σ), one chamber of the apparatus was filled with the particular solution of the solute and the other one with pure distilled water. A pressure head of pure water was applied on the side of water-chamber whereas the capillary was attached to the chamber containing solution to note the net (resultant) volume flow.

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